

A SEQUENT CALCULUS FOR SATISFIABILITY AND VALIDITY

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Abstract. This paper presents a new sequent calculus that integrates rules for testing both satisfiability and validity within the same logical system. Its notion of deduction encompasses both nonlogical and logical assumptions. A formula is considered *consistent* when it has a certain deduction from nonlogical assumptions, and it is considered *provable* if there is a certain deduction for it from logical assumptions. The equivalences between provability and validity, as well as between consistency and satisfiability, are proved. All the structural rules are admissible, and extensions with nonlogical rules are shown to overcome Post-completeness.

§1. Introduction.

1.1. Problem. Satisfiability is a well-established concept in mathematical logic, but it is usually explored in automated reasoning [1], which is a main area of artificial intelligence. Its dual concept, validity, is typically studied through a syntactic notion of provability. There are two fundamental principles that ground the interplay between satisfiability and provability. The *principle of directness* says that a formula α is consistent if, and only if, α is satisfiable. The *principle of indirectness* states that α is satisfiable if, and only if, $\neg\alpha$ is not provable. The principle of indirectness is the basis of the resolution calculus and tableaux systems, for instance, which are the common logical systems behind SAT (Propositional Satisfiability Problem) and SMT (Satisfiability Modulo Theory) solvers and ATP (Automated Theorem Proving) systems. The principle of directness is, however, unexplored. Indeed, most SAT solvers have parameters to customize the choice of solutions to family of instances, because different strategies work well for different types of combinatorial problems [3]. SMT solvers and ATP systems are usually integrated with SAT solvers via the principle of indirectness. The main bottleneck of this indirect approach is that the adjustment of parameters and the interpretation of them are theoretically hard to couple with and practically increase the complexity of finding solutions [8][9]. The problems that SMT solvers and ATP systems deal with already involve theoretically intractable computational complexity classes [11], and its practical relation with SAT solvers via the principle of indirectness makes things much worse.

Key words and phrases. Proof theory; Satisfiability; Provability; Sequent Calculus.

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Given that, the *foundational problem* of this article is: How can we integrate satisfiability and provability without using the principle of indirectness? Of course, any answer must be based on the principle of directness, but how?

1.2. Thesis. We propose a *Hilbertian approach* to integrate satisfiability and validity in a unique and uniform system. From this perspective, it must be true a kind of total directness existent in Hilbert's days, namely: we must be able to pass from the syntactic and semantic dimensions of logic without using indirect ways, but still keeping clear the distinction between these dimensions, as Tarski has established [20]. More precisely, this article takes the position that Gentzen's structural proof theory [16] should be extended to encompass provability and consistency together in a system \mathcal{S} for which we can prove a *principle of total directness*: α is satisfiable if, and only if, α is consistent in \mathcal{S} and α is valid if, and only if, α is provable in \mathcal{S} .

The *main thesis* to be sustained here has two parts: (1) The concept of deduction within sequent calculus should be extended to work not only with axioms (logical assumptions) as usual but also with postulates (nonlogical assumptions); (2) The rules of inference that combine consistency and provability must preserve consistency. For instance, the first deduction scheme below must be an indubitable deduction as far as classical logic reasoning is concerned. By its turn, the second, third and fourth must be acceptable deductions, but the last one must be unacceptable:

$$\begin{array}{ccccc}
 \rho \vdash \rho & \vdash \rho & \vdash \eta & \rho \vdash & \vdash \eta & \vdash \rho & \eta \vdash & \rho \vdash & \eta \vdash \\
 \vdots & \vdots \\
 \hline
 \vdash \rho \vee \neg \rho & \vdash \rho \vee \eta & \vdash \rho \vee \eta
 \end{array}$$

The elementary nature of this thesis may covers up its deepness, but classical propositional logic is Post-complete; meaning that whenever a non-tautological formula is added as a new axiom schema, the resulting system is inconsistent [23][p.17]. This makes the formalization of the envisaged main thesis a hard matter. In what follows we show how a Hilbertian perspective can overcome the limitation imposed by Post-completeness.

1.3. Results. The aim is to develop a Hilbertian approach to the interplay between consistency-provability and satisfiability-validity; a new theory in which the logic syntax and semantic are symmetric. Visually:

Mathematical logic universe

In Section 2, a sequent calculus for classical propositional logic capable of characterizing both consistency and provability is introduced. In this approach, *assumptions* are sequents with at most one occurrence of a propositional variable

in each side: the *postulates* have one occurrence of the formula either to the left or to the right, whereas the *axioms* have one occurrence of it on both sides. Hence, there are two notions of deduction, namely: *postulative deductions* are built from postulates, *axiomatic deductions* are built from axioms. A formula is *consistent* when there is a verification (right postulative deduction) for it, and it is *provable* if there is a proof (right axiomatic deduction) for it. The admissibility of the weakening rules in the sequent calculus is proved. We also show the equivalence between provability and validity (Theorem 2.1); the first basis of our Hilbertian perspective.

We made an exhaustive search, but found no work similar to ours. However, the idea of extension of sequent calculae with nonlogical axioms dates back to Gentzen works [5], and has been developed with nonlogical rules by Uesu [21] and Negri & von Plato [15]; the later extensively studied this perspective in [17]. Negri and von Plato did not explore a notion of consistency of formulas from the point of view of nonlogical assumptions. Similarly, Piazza & Pulcini [14] studied supraclassical logic obtained via the addition of nonlogical assumptions, without considering classical systems neither mentioning the interplay between consistency and provability. Takemura [19] also made a sequent calculus with assumptions, but again with same characteristics of Piazza & Pulcini.

In Section 3, we present two results. First, we prove the admissibility of contraction in the calculus introduced. Then, we show the equivalence between consistency and satisfiability (Theorem 3.2); the second basis of our Hilbertian approach. Its proof uses a definition of consistency internal to the sequent calculus, namely, existence of a verification, and not an external metatheoretical assertion that defines the consistency of a formula as non-derivability of a contradiction. Makinson's [10] notion of consistent extension of partial evaluations to total ones and its syntactic counterpart (called *sympathy*) is related but quite different, because we present an explicit syntactic calculus.

In Section 4, we show that the structural rules are admissible, but have a different role in our Hilbertian approach. In special, Theorem 4.2 shows that the weakening rule has a deep connection with the construction of models - postulative deductions from the point of view of our framework. Besides, we show in Theorem 4.1 that Girard's assertion in [6][p.125] that sequent calculus with non-logical assumptions cannot hold the cut elimination is not true for the sequent calculus defined here - we will show it holds.

In Section 5, we provide another proof of Hilbert & Ackermann's Post-completeness of classical propositional logic [2][p.43]. From this, we show a limitative result for Negri & vonPlato's approach to rule extensions of classical propositional logic (Theorem 5.1). This limitation is overcome within sequent calculus, since it can be extended by adding nonlogical rules as well as nonlogical assumptions. Hence, the mathematical foundations to directly integrate SAT, SMT and ATP systems will be established, a subject explored in the conclusion.

§2. Equivalence between provability and validity with consistency in the middle. In this section, our aim is to integrate consistency and provability in one sequent calculus. We assume that \mathcal{F} is the set of *propositional formulas* recursively defined on the set of basic propositions \mathcal{E} , which we call *elementary*

propositions, using the regular connectives \neg , \wedge , \vee and \rightarrow to make complex formulas, which we call *composite formulas*. The *composition* of a formula is the number of connectives in it. We use ρ and η as metavariables for elements and α , β and γ for propositional formulas in general (elementary or composite), or variations of these symbols when necessary. $\mathcal{E}(\alpha)$ denotes the set of elementary formulas in α .

DEFINITION 2.1. A sequent is the empty list \emptyset or a pair (Γ, Δ) made of two multisets Γ (the antecedent) and Δ (the succedent) of formulas in \mathcal{F} .

We call the empty list \emptyset by *empty sequent*. We use the symbol $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$ to denote sequents. As usual we will always list the formulas on both sides of the sequents. The sequents (Γ, \emptyset) , (\emptyset, Δ) , (\emptyset, \emptyset) will be, respectively, represented by $\Gamma \vdash$, $\vdash \Delta$ and \vdash . We name \vdash as *absurd sequent*. Note that the concept of sequent does not presuppose the finiteness of the left and right multisets. In what follows everything will be finite, but this is a consequence of the finitary nature of the formulas considered and not a restriction of the methods developed.

DEFINITION 2.2. A rule is pair (Φ, Ψ) formed by a set of sequents Φ called the premisses and a sequent Ψ called the conclusion.

We represent a rule R by listing its premisses and conclusion separated by a vertical bar like this $\Gamma_1 \vdash \Delta_1, \dots, \Gamma_n \vdash \Delta_n \mid_R \Gamma \vdash \Delta$ or by a horizontal bar:

$$\frac{\Gamma_1 \vdash \Delta_1 \quad \dots \quad \Gamma_n \vdash \Delta_n}{\Gamma \vdash \Delta} R$$

If the context is clear, we omit the subscript R in \mid_R . In a rule that has a premiss like $\Gamma, \alpha \vdash \Delta$ or $\Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta$, we call α the *principal formula* of the rule and Γ and Δ the *contexts* of the sequent.

DEFINITION 2.3. A derivation D is a tree whose nodes are sequents such that:

1. Each leaf of D is the empty sequent;
2. Each node in D is obtained from previous nodes in D by rules that are the edges of D .

The root of D can be an arbitrary sequent $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$, but when it is of the form $\Gamma \vdash$ then D is called a left derivation, and in case of $\vdash \Delta$ we call D a right derivation. The height of a branch in a derivation D is the number of rules in it, counting from its leaf to its last sequent. The height of a derivation is the greatest height of all the branches in D . The height of a sequent $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$ in a derivation D is the greatest height of all the branches in D that end in $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$.

In practice we omit the empty sequents from derivations, calling the sequents connected to the empty sequents as *leaves* of the derivations.

DEFINITION 2.4. Assumptions are sequents with at most one elementary formula $\rho \in \mathcal{E}$ on each side. The postulates have one element either to the left or to the right, whereas the axioms have one element on both sides and they are equal. The postulates and axioms are called proper assumptions. A postulate $\rho \vdash$ is said to be negative about ρ , and $\vdash \rho$ is positive about ρ . An axiom $\rho \vdash \rho$ is said to be neutral about ρ . Two proper assumptions about ρ are consistent if it

does not happen that one is negative and the other positive about ρ . A foliage is a set of proper assumptions, and it is said to be consistent if its assumptions are consistent. A deduction is a derivation whose leaves form a consistent foliage. An axiomatic deduction is a deduction whose foliage has only axioms, and a postulative deduction has only postulates in its foliage. A proper deduction is either axiomatic or postulative deduction.

The definition of proper deduction excludes some possibilities. At first, assumptions of the form $\rho \vdash \sigma$ with $\rho \neq \sigma$ are not proper deductions, because they are not proper assumptions. If we restrict our attention to proper assumptions, we find even so that there are deductions that are not proper even so, namely, those that have postulates and axioms in their foliages. We have chosen to exclude these possibilities because the focus is on the syntactic counterparts of the semantic concepts of satisfiability (postulative deductions) and validity (axiomatic deductions). Thus, from now on we just write *deductions*, but we mean *proper deductions*, because our study is restrict to them.

DEFINITION 2.5. A sequent calculus \mathcal{C} is a set of rules. The (sequent system $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{C})$ over a sequent calculus \mathcal{C} is the set of deductions that uses only the rules of \mathcal{C} . We say that a sequent $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$ is deducible in a sequent calculus \mathcal{C} if there is a deduction in $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{C})$ whose conclusion is $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$. A proof in \mathcal{C} is a right axiomatic deduction, and a refutation is a left one. A verification in \mathcal{C} is a right postulative proof, and a falsification is a left one. A formula α is a provable in \mathcal{C} if there is a proof of it, and α is consistent in \mathcal{C} if there is a verification of it.¹

In the definition about, we should specify that we are working in *sequent calculus* because we allow axiomatic and postulative rules, but we will ommit the qualification for the sake of simplicity, when the context makes clear what we are talking about. Besides, hereafter, we will write \mathcal{S} instead of $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{C})$, when the context makes clear which one is the generating calculus. To be precise, the sequent calculus \mathcal{C} that generates an sequent system $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{C})$ has three kinds of rules: (1) the *connective rules* allows us to deduce formulas with connectives; (2) the *axiomatic rules* have axioms as their premisses; (3) the *postulative rules* have postulates as their premisses. Hence, in order to specify a sequent system, we just need to provide these rules. Let us do it for classical propositional logic.

DEFINITION 2.6. The classical propositional system $\mathcal{CP}(\mathcal{C})$ is such that \mathcal{C} has the following connective rules:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta}{\Gamma, \neg\alpha \vdash \Delta} \neg_L \qquad \frac{\Gamma, \alpha \vdash \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \neg\alpha, \Delta} \neg_R$$

$$\frac{\Gamma, \alpha, \beta \vdash \Delta}{\Gamma, \alpha \wedge \beta \vdash \Delta} \wedge_L \qquad \frac{\Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta \quad \Gamma \vdash \beta, \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \alpha \wedge \beta, \Delta} \wedge_R$$

¹In [18][p.9-28] Poincaré distinguishes between demonstrations and verifications, the former are creative processes whereas the later are calculative one. We are using Poincaré's terminology, but in the context of propositional logic.

$$\frac{\Gamma, \alpha \vdash \Delta \quad \Gamma, \beta \vdash \Delta}{\Gamma, \alpha \vee \beta \vdash \Delta} \vee_L \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash \alpha, \beta, \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \alpha \vee \beta, \Delta} \vee_R$$

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta \quad \Gamma, \beta \vdash \Delta}{\Gamma, \alpha \rightarrow \beta \vdash \Delta} \rightarrow_L \quad \frac{\Gamma, \alpha \vdash \beta, \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \alpha \rightarrow \beta, \Delta} \rightarrow_R$$

The axiomatics rules of \mathcal{C} are these:

$$\frac{}{\rho \vdash \rho} Ax$$

$$\frac{\eta \vdash \eta \quad \Gamma \vdash \Delta}{\eta, \Gamma \vdash \Delta} G_L \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash \Delta \quad \rho \vdash \rho}{\Gamma \vdash \Delta, \rho} G_R$$

The postulative rules of \mathcal{C} are these:

$$\frac{}{\rho \vdash} P_L \quad \frac{}{\vdash \rho} P_R$$

$$\frac{\eta \vdash \quad \Gamma \vdash \Delta}{\eta, \Gamma \vdash \Delta} J_L \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash \Delta \quad \vdash \rho}{\Gamma \vdash \Delta, \rho} J_R$$

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \Delta \quad \vdash \rho}{\rho, \Gamma \vdash \Delta} S_L \quad \frac{\eta \vdash \quad \Gamma \vdash \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \Delta, \eta} S_R$$

In the axiomatic and postulative rules above, we assume that Γ and Δ are multisets of elementary formulas. We call G_L and G_R the merge rules, J_L and J_R the joint rules, S_L and S_R the cross rules.

The meaning of these rules must be self-explanatory, but let us appreciate an example to make things concrete.

EXAMPLE 2.1. In the system \mathcal{CP} we can make the following verifications for a disjunction $\rho \vee \eta$:

$$\frac{\frac{}{\vdash \rho} P_R \quad \frac{}{\vdash \eta} P_R}{\vdash \rho, \eta} J_R}{\vdash \rho \vee \eta} \vee_R \quad \frac{\frac{}{\eta \vdash} P_L \quad \frac{}{\vdash \rho} P_R}{\vdash \rho, \eta} S_R}{\vdash \rho \vee \eta} \vee_R \quad \frac{\frac{}{\rho \vdash} P_L \quad \frac{}{\vdash \eta} P_R}{\vdash \rho, \eta} S_R}{\vdash \rho \vee \eta} \vee_R$$

Nonetheless, there is no deduction of $\vdash \rho \vee \eta$ with foliage $\rho \vdash$ and $\eta \vdash$. Indeed, J_L gives $\rho, \eta \vdash$, and S_R results in $\rho \vdash \eta$ or $\eta \vdash \rho$, depending on whether we see $\rho \vdash$ first and $\eta \vdash$ second.

Besides, there is a postulative and an axiomatic deduction of $\vdash \rho \vee \neg \rho$ in \mathcal{CP} :

$$\frac{\frac{}{\rho \vdash} P_L \quad \frac{}{\rho \vdash} P_L}{\rho \vdash \rho} S_R}{\vdash \rho, \neg \rho} \neg_R \quad \frac{\frac{}{\rho \vdash \rho} Ax}{\vdash \rho, \neg \rho} \neg_R}{\vdash \rho \vee \neg \rho} \vee_R$$

The example above shows \mathcal{CP} meets the intuitive requirement that we mentioned at the introduction of this article. The fundamental idea is that the postulative and axiomatic rules allow us to do what the weakening rule does in a regular sequent calculus, but with one subtle and important difference, expressed in the next proposition.

PROPOSITION 2.1. *If ρ is an elementary formula that occurs in the conclusion of a deduction D in \mathcal{CP} , then ρ occurs in the foliage of D .*

PROOF. By induction on the height h of D . For $h = 1$, there are three possible deductions:

$$\frac{}{\rho \vdash} P_L \quad \frac{}{\rho \vdash \rho} Ax \quad \frac{}{\vdash \rho} P_R$$

For each of these deductions, the result is true. If we get a deduction of height $h = k + 1$ by applying the rules $\wedge_L, \wedge_R, \vee_L, \vee_R, \rightarrow_L, \rightarrow_R, \neg_L$ or \neg_R , then the result is true due to the induction hypothesis and the fact that these rules do not add new elementary formulas in the conclusion, yet they just add a connective to formulas already given in the premises. If the rule G_L, G_R, J_L, J_R, S_L or S_R is used to obtain a deduction of height $h = k + 1$, then the induction hypothesis again guarantees the result because these rules add an elementary formula ρ but ρ occurs in a premise that is an assumption, which means ρ already is, by definition, in the foliage. \dashv

One of the key aspects of proof theory of provability is the study of admissibility and eliminability of rules. We extend this to the context of double sequents as well.

DEFINITION 2.7. *Let \mathcal{C} be a sequent calculus, and let R be the rule $\Gamma_1 \vdash \Delta_1, \dots, \Gamma_n \vdash \Delta_n \mid \Gamma \vdash \Delta$. If R is not an axiomatic (postulative) rule of \mathcal{C} , R is said to be axiomatic (postulative) admissible in \mathcal{S} if $\Gamma_i \vdash \Delta_i$ to be provable (consistent) in $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{C})$ for every i with $1 \leq i \leq n$ implies $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$ to be provable (consistent) in $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{C})$. Besides, if R is an axiomatic (postulative) rule of \mathcal{C} , we say that R is axiomatic (postulative) eliminable from \mathcal{S} if $\Gamma_i \vdash \Delta_i$ to be provable (consistent) in $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{C} \setminus R)$ for every i with $1 \leq i \leq n$ implies $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$ to be provable (consistent) in $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{C} \setminus R)$.*

We need one more notion before to prove the first substantive result.

DEFINITION 2.8. *A stem in a deduction D is a sequent of the form $\rho_1, \dots, \rho_m \vdash \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n$ in which only elementary formulas occur and there is no sequent $\rho'_1, \dots, \rho'_r \vdash \eta'_1, \dots, \eta'_s$ in D with only elementary formulas too such that*

$$\frac{\rho_1, \dots, \rho_m \vdash \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n}{\rho'_1, \dots, \rho'_r \vdash \eta'_1, \dots, \eta'_s}$$

is an edge in D . A limb of a deduction D is a subtree of D whose root is a stem. Given a deduction D of $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$ the stem decomposition of $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$ in D , in symbols $\mathcal{T}(D)$, is the set of stems of D .

The notion of stem decomposition is well-defined because the postulative and axiomatic rules can only be applied after, from bottom up, all connective rules

were applied. From now on, we write $\mathcal{O}(D)$ to denote the foliage of a deduction D .

DEFINITION 2.9. *The weakening rules are the following rules:*

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \Delta}{\Gamma, \alpha \vdash \Delta} W_L \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta} W_R$$

for every formula α and finite multisets of formulas Γ, Δ of \mathcal{F} .

LEMMA 2.1. *The weakening rules W_L and W_R are admissible in \mathcal{CP} .*

PROOF. We prove a stronger statement by induction on the composition of α : given $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$ deducible in \mathcal{CP} , for every Γ', Δ' such that $\Gamma \subseteq \Gamma'$ and $\Delta \subseteq \Delta'$, if $\Gamma' \vdash \Delta'$ is deducible in \mathcal{CP} , then $\Gamma', \alpha \vdash \Delta'$ and $\Gamma' \vdash \alpha, \Delta'$ is deducible in \mathcal{CP} . In virtue of $\Gamma \subseteq \Gamma'$ and $\Delta \subseteq \Delta'$, the lemma is a special case of this strong result.

Suppose that $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$ is deducible in \mathcal{CP} and, for $\Gamma \subseteq \Gamma'$ and $\Delta \subseteq \Delta'$, D is a deduction of $\Gamma' \vdash \Delta'$ in \mathcal{CP} . For α an elementary formula ρ , we consider:

$$\begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(D) \\ \vdots \\ \Gamma' \vdash \Delta' \end{array}$$

Then we take the first, from the left to the right, stem $\rho_1, \dots, \rho_m \vdash \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n$ in the stem decomposition $\mathcal{T}(D)$. Let $\mathcal{O}(D_1)$ be the subfoliage of the limb associated to this stem. For D a postulative deduction, if $\mathcal{O}(D_1) \cup \{\vdash \rho\}$ is consistent, we form the deductions bellow from the original subdeduction of $\rho_1, \dots, \rho_m \vdash \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n$ in D :

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(D_1) \\ \vdots \\ \rho_1, \dots, \rho_m \vdash \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n \end{array} \quad \frac{}{\vdash \rho} P_R}{\rho_1, \dots, \rho_m, \rho \vdash \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n} S_L \quad \frac{\begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(D_1) \\ \vdots \\ \rho_1, \dots, \rho_m \vdash \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n \end{array} \quad \frac{}{\vdash \rho} P_R}{\rho_1, \dots, \rho_m \vdash \rho, \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n} J_R$$

If $\mathcal{O}(D_1) \cup \{\vdash \rho\}$ is not consistent, we make the dual of the above with $\rho \vdash$. If D is instead an axiomatic proof, we do this:

$$\frac{\frac{}{\rho \vdash \rho} Ax \quad \begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(D_1) \\ \vdots \\ \rho_1, \dots, \rho_m \vdash \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n \end{array}}{\rho_1, \dots, \rho_m, \rho \vdash \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n} G_L \quad \frac{\begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(D_1) \\ \vdots \\ \rho_1, \dots, \rho_m \vdash \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n \end{array} \quad \frac{}{\rho \vdash \rho} Ax}{\rho_1, \dots, \rho_m \vdash \rho, \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n} G_R$$

In virtue of the consistency of D , we can do the same procedure to each stem in $\mathcal{T}(D)$, obtaining subdeductions D_1, \dots, D_w of stems Φ_1, \dots, Φ_w equal to the ones in $\mathcal{T}(D)$, except by the fact that they have ρ added to right. After that, we apply to Φ_1, \dots, Φ_w the same connective rules as in D and get the conclusion $\Gamma' \vdash \rho, \Delta'$. To get $\Gamma', \rho \vdash \Delta'$ we make the dual procedure.

For α a negation $\neg\beta$, we have

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(A) \\ \vdots \\ \Gamma' \vdash \Delta' \\ \hline \Gamma', \beta \vdash \Delta' \end{array}}{\Gamma' \vdash \neg\beta, \Delta'} \neg_R \qquad \frac{\begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(B) \\ \vdots \\ \Gamma' \vdash \Delta' \\ \hline \Gamma' \vdash \beta, \Delta' \end{array}}{\Gamma', \neg\beta \vdash \Delta'} \neg_L$$

where the deductions A of $\Gamma', \beta \vdash \Delta'$ and B of $\Gamma' \vdash \beta, \Delta'$ were got via the induction hypothesis.

For α a conjunction $\beta \wedge \gamma$, we have to the left

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(D) \\ \vdots \\ \Gamma' \vdash \Delta' \\ \hline \Gamma', \beta \vdash \Delta' \\ \hline \Gamma', \beta, \gamma \vdash \Delta' \end{array}}{\Gamma', \beta \wedge \gamma \vdash \Delta'} \wedge_L$$

where we applied the induction hypothesis twice: first on the context Γ' , and then on the context $\Gamma'' = \Gamma', \beta$ in order to get the deduction D of $\Gamma', \beta, \gamma \vdash \Delta'$. We can do that because by hypothesis the result is true for every context that contains Γ and Δ . To the right we have:

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(A) \\ \vdots \\ \Gamma' \vdash \Delta' \\ \hline \Gamma' \vdash \beta, \Delta' \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(B) \\ \vdots \\ \Gamma' \vdash \Delta' \\ \hline \Gamma' \vdash \gamma, \Delta' \end{array}}{\Gamma' \vdash \beta \wedge \gamma, \Delta'} \wedge_R$$

where the induction hypothesis generated the deductions A of $\Gamma \vdash \beta, \Delta$ and B of $\Gamma \vdash \gamma, \Delta$.

For α a disjunction $\beta \vee \gamma$ or an implication $\beta \rightarrow \gamma$, we proceed like in the case of conjunction. \dashv

Since we have proved the admissibility of the weakening rules, hereafter we will freely use, for the sake of brevity. Let us finish this section with the first basis in the foundations of the sequent calculus \mathcal{CP} : the equivalence between provability and validity.

DEFINITION 2.10. *Let $\mathcal{S}(\alpha)$ be the set of subformulas of the formula α . A valuation for α is a function $\chi : \mathcal{S}(\alpha) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ such that, for every $\neg\beta, \beta \wedge \gamma, \beta \vee \gamma, \beta \rightarrow \gamma \in \mathcal{S}(\alpha)$, we have $\chi(\neg\beta) = 1$ if, and only if, $\chi(\beta) = 0$, $\chi(\beta \wedge \gamma) = 1$ if, and only if, $\chi(\beta) = 1$ and $\chi(\gamma) = 1$, $\chi(\beta \vee \gamma) = 1$ if, and only if, $\chi(\beta) = 1$ or $\chi(\gamma) = 1$, and $\chi(\beta \rightarrow \gamma) = 1$ if, and only if, $\chi(\beta) = 1$ implies $\chi(\gamma) = 1$. A formula α is satisfiable if there is a valuation χ for α such that $\chi(\alpha) = 1$. A formula α is valid if all valuations χ for α are such that $\chi(\alpha) = 1$.²*

²Note that we are defining valuations as finite functions, restricted to the subformulas of a given formula. Usually, valuations are infinite functions defined over all elementary formulas,

THEOREM 2.1. *For every formula α in \mathcal{F} , α is provable in \mathcal{CP} if, and only if, α is valid.*

PROOF. The axiomatic rules of \mathcal{CP} are a variant of the $G3cp$ sequent calculus exhibited in [16][p.49], except by one difference³ $G3cp$ has this general Ax^* :

$$\frac{}{\Gamma, \alpha \vdash \alpha, \Delta} Ax^*$$

$G3cp$ is a sound and complete calculus for classical propositional logic. Thus, to show that α is provable in \mathcal{CP} if, and only if, α is valid, it is sufficient to prove that Ax^* is admissible in \mathcal{CP} . We proceed by induction on the composition of α . For α an elementary formula ρ , let $\Gamma = \{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_m\}$ and $\Delta = \{\delta_1, \dots, \delta_n\}$. The result holds in this case as exhibited in the proof bellow:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{}{\rho \vdash \rho} Ax}{\gamma_1, \rho \vdash \rho} W_L}{\vdots} W_L}{\frac{\frac{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_m, \rho \vdash \rho}{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_m, \rho \vdash \rho, \delta_1} W_R}{\vdots} W_R} \frac{\gamma_1, \dots, \gamma_m, \rho \vdash \rho, \delta_1, \dots, \delta_n}{\Gamma, \rho \vdash \rho, \Delta} W_R$$

For α an implication $\beta \rightarrow \gamma$, the induction hypothesis gives us an axiomatic deduction A of $\Gamma, \beta \vdash \beta, \Delta$ and an axiomatic deduction B of $\Gamma, \gamma \vdash \gamma, \Delta$. From this, we can do:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\mathcal{O}(A)}{\vdots} \Gamma, \beta \vdash \beta, \Delta \quad \frac{\mathcal{O}(B)}{\vdots} \Gamma, \gamma \vdash \gamma, \Delta}{\Gamma, \beta \rightarrow \gamma, \beta \vdash \gamma, \Delta} \rightarrow_L}{\Gamma, \beta \rightarrow \gamma \vdash \beta \rightarrow \gamma, \Delta} \rightarrow_R$$

We know the deduction above is axiomatic because both A and B are too. The reasoning for α a negation, conjunction and disjunction is analogous. \dashv

§3. Equivalence between consistency and satisfiability. In this section, we prove the equivalence between consistency and satisfiability. Along the way, we prove the admissibility of contraction rules as well. The proof of the equivalence between consistency and satisfiability has two steps. In the first one we

but we know that there is no lost of generality in our definition, for we need to evaluate only the elementary formulas that occur in a given formula [7][p.118].

³To be precise, $G3cp$ has the absurd operator \perp , and thus a rule for it, instead of the negation operator \neg and its rules as in \mathcal{CP} . It is well known, however, that this two formulations are equivalent (Cf. chapter 2 of [16]).

show a lemma associated with a basic problem that can be appreciated with a little example.

EXAMPLE 3.1. *Consider the following deduction of the disjunction $\vdash a \vee (b \wedge c)$:*

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{}{\vdash a} P_R \quad \frac{}{\vdash b} P_R}{\vdash a, b} J_R \quad \frac{\frac{}{\vdash a} P_R \quad \frac{}{\vdash c} P_R}{\vdash a, c} J_R}{\vdash a, (b \wedge c)} \wedge_R}{\vdash a \vee (b \wedge c)} \vee_R$$

As it is illustrated above, in a deduction of a disjunction we know that there is a subdeduction of a sequent with its disjunct both to the right, in this case $\vdash a, (b \wedge c)$, because we must have applied \vee_R to the disjunction. Does this imply that each disjunct also has a deduction? In the example above the deduction itself has a subdeduction of one disjunct, $\vdash a$, but it does not have the other, $(b \wedge c)$. Nonetheless, there is an axiomatic deduction of $\rho \vee \neg\rho$, namely:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{}{\rho \vdash \rho} Ax}{\vdash \rho, \neg\rho} \neg_R}{\vdash \rho \vee \neg\rho} \vee_R$$

But there is no axiomatic deduction of ρ . We need to determine, then, what are the kinds of subdeductions that exist for a given deductions. For this, we define the concept of compatibility between deductions.

DEFINITION 3.1. *Given a deduction D , we say that $\mathcal{O}(D)$ is positive (negative) about an elementary formula $\rho \in \mathcal{E}$ if there is an assumption $\Phi \in \mathcal{O}(D)$ such that Φ is positive (negative) on ρ . A deduction E is compatible with a deduction D when the fact that $\mathcal{O}(E)$ is positive on ρ implies that $\mathcal{O}(D)$ is positive or neutral on ρ and if $\mathcal{O}(E)$ is negative on ρ , then $\mathcal{O}(D)$ is negative or neutral on ρ .*

Note that a proof E can be compatible with a proof D , but even so there is an elementary formula for which $\mathcal{O}(D)$ is positive or negative but $\mathcal{O}(E)$ does not.

LEMMA 3.1. *For every deduction D and multiset of formulas $\Gamma \cup \Delta$ and formulas α and β , the following statements are true:*

- (1) *If $\Gamma, \alpha, \beta \vdash \Delta$ is in D , then there is a postulative deduction of $\Gamma, \alpha \vdash \Delta$ and there is a postulative deduction of $\Gamma, \beta \vdash \Delta$, both compatible with D .*
- (2) *If $\Gamma \vdash \alpha, \beta, \Delta$ is in D , then there is a postulative deduction of $\Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta$ and there is a postulative deduction of $\Gamma \vdash \beta, \Delta$, both compatible with D .*
- (3) *If $\Gamma, \alpha \vdash \beta, \Delta$ is in D , then there is a postulative deduction of $\Gamma, \alpha \vdash \Delta$ and there is a postulative deduction of $\Gamma \vdash \beta, \Delta$, both compatible with D .*

PROOF. We will construct new deductions A (height h_A) for α as principal and B (height h_B) for β as principal. The construction are made by induction on the height h_D of D for the statements (1), (2) and (3) together. If $h_D = 1$, the unique possibility is a deduction with just one rule Ax , which is the case of statement (3). In this situation, $\Gamma = \Delta = \emptyset$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{E}$, say $\alpha = \rho$ and $\beta = \rho$ and D is the proof:

$$\frac{}{\rho \vdash \rho} Ax$$

We make the deductions A and B bellow:

$$\frac{}{\rho \vdash} P_L \quad \frac{}{\vdash \rho} P_R$$

The deductions A and B are compatible with D . The base of the induction that includes also the statements (1) and (2) must be for $h_D = 2$, because the lemma is about two formulas in the conclusion. Let us consider this case. We have again $\Gamma = \Delta = \emptyset$ or Γ and Δ are singletons and $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{E}$, say $\alpha = \rho$ and $\beta = \eta$. If the last rule is G_L or G_R , we have the possibilities bellow for D because it must have axioms in its foliage:

$$\frac{\frac{}{\rho \vdash \rho} Ax \quad \frac{}{\eta \vdash \eta} Ax}{\rho, \eta \vdash} G_L \quad \frac{\frac{}{\rho \vdash \rho} Ax \quad \frac{}{\eta \vdash \eta} Ax}{\rho \vdash \rho, \eta} G_R$$

Depending on what we take as the context, we may have an instance statement (1), (2) or (3). For instance, in the first deduction, if $\Gamma = \{\rho\}$ or $\Gamma = \{\eta\}$, then it is an instance of statement (3), but if $\Delta = \{\eta\}$, it is an instance of (2). We have this freedom to change what is considered the context because the result is true for all of them. Anyway, we can get the desired deductions A or B by just applying the postulate rules P_L and P_R .

If the last rule is J_L or J_R , we have these possibilities for D :

$$\frac{\frac{}{\rho \vdash} P_L \quad \frac{}{\eta \vdash} P_L}{\rho, \eta \vdash} J_L \quad \frac{\frac{}{\rho \vdash} P_L \quad \frac{}{\vdash \eta} P_L}{\rho \vdash \eta} J_L \quad \frac{\frac{}{\rho \vdash} P_L \quad \frac{}{\vdash \eta} P_R}{\rho \vdash \eta} J_R \quad \frac{\frac{}{\vdash \rho} P_R \quad \frac{}{\vdash \eta} P_R}{\vdash \rho, \eta} J_R$$

As it can be saw in the case of the joint rules, we again get the desired deductions A or B by just applying the postulate rules P_L and P_R .

If the last rule is S_L or S_R , we have these possibilities for D :

$$\frac{\frac{}{\vdash \rho} P_R \quad \frac{}{\vdash \eta} P_R}{\eta \vdash \rho} S_L \quad \frac{\frac{}{\rho \vdash} P_L \quad \frac{}{\vdash \eta} P_L}{\rho, \eta \vdash} S_L \quad \frac{\frac{}{\rho \vdash} P_L \quad \frac{}{\eta \vdash} P_L}{\eta \vdash \rho} S_R \quad \frac{\frac{}{\rho \vdash} P_L \quad \frac{}{\vdash \eta} P_L}{\vdash \rho, \eta} S_R$$

Again we can get the desired deductions A or B by just applying the postulate rules P_L and P_R .

For $h = k + 1$, with $k \geq 2$, we analyze the last rule applied in D in the statements (1), (2) and (3) to pass from a deduction of height k , for which the result is true by the induction hypothesis, to a deduction of height $k + 1$. The proof for the statements (1) and (2) are dual to each other, and the proof of (3) is a straightforward combination of both. We will exhibit the details for the statement (2). In this case, there is a deduction of height $k + 1$, namely:

$$\frac{\mathcal{O}(D)}{\Gamma \vdash \alpha, \beta, \Delta}$$

If the last rule R is applied to get a formula γ in $\Gamma \cup \Delta$, say that $\Gamma \cup \Delta = \Gamma' \cup \Delta' \cup \{\gamma\}$, we use the induction hypothesis to obtain $\Gamma' \vdash \alpha, \Delta'$ and $\Gamma' \vdash \beta, \Delta'$, and then apply R to take $\Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta$ and $\Gamma \vdash \beta, \Delta$. Thus, it is enough to focus in the cases in which the last rule is applied to get α or β . Without loss of generality, suppose we applied a rule to get α . If this rule is \wedge_R , then the deduction D actually is:

$$\frac{\frac{\mathcal{O}(D')}{\vdots} \quad \frac{\mathcal{O}(D'')}{\vdots}}{\frac{\Gamma \vdash \alpha', \beta, \Delta \quad \Gamma \vdash \alpha'', \beta, \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \alpha' \wedge \alpha'', \beta, \Delta} \wedge_R}$$

where $\mathcal{O}(D) = \mathcal{O}(D') \cup \mathcal{O}(D'')$. The induction hypothesis of statement (2) gives us four possible deductions compatible with D :

$$\frac{\frac{\mathcal{O}(A')}{\vdots}}{\Gamma \vdash \alpha', \Delta} \quad \frac{\mathcal{O}(B')}{\vdots} \quad \frac{\mathcal{O}(A'')}{\vdots} \quad \frac{\mathcal{O}(B'')}{\vdots}$$

The second and fourth deductions give us $\Gamma \vdash \beta, \Delta$, and we get a deduction of $\Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta$ by making the following with the first and third deductions:

$$\frac{\frac{\mathcal{O}(A')}{\vdots} \quad \frac{\mathcal{O}(A'')}{\vdots}}{\frac{\Gamma \vdash \alpha', \Delta \quad \Gamma \vdash \alpha'', \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \alpha' \wedge \alpha'', \Delta} \wedge_R}$$

If the last rule is \vee_R , then the deduction D is:

$$\frac{\frac{\mathcal{O}(D)}{\vdots}}{\frac{\Gamma \vdash \alpha', \alpha'', \beta, \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \alpha' \vee \alpha'', \beta, \Delta} \vee_R}$$

Considering the context $\Delta' = \beta, \Delta$, the induction hypothesis of statement (2) gives us two deductions compatible with D :

$$\frac{\mathcal{O}(A)}{\vdots} \quad \frac{\mathcal{O}(B)}{\vdots}$$

Let us think about the first deduction, for the reasoning is analogous in case the induction hypothesis generates the second one. Applying again the induction hypothesis of statement (2) on the first deduction above, we have two new deductions:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\mathcal{O}(A')}{\vdots}}{\Gamma \vdash \alpha', \Delta} \quad \frac{\mathcal{O}(B')}{\vdots}}{\Gamma \vdash \alpha', \alpha'', \Delta} W_R \quad \frac{\mathcal{O}(B')}{\Gamma \vdash \beta, \Delta}}{\Gamma \vdash \alpha' \vee \alpha'', \Delta} \vee_R$$

If the last rule is \rightarrow_R , then P is the deduction:

$$\frac{\frac{\mathcal{O}(D)}{\vdots}}{\Gamma, \alpha' \vdash \alpha'', \beta, \Delta}}{\Gamma \vdash \alpha' \rightarrow \alpha'', \beta, \Delta} \rightarrow_R$$

The induction hypothesis of statement (2) over the context $\Gamma' = \Gamma, \alpha'$ provides two deductions:

$$\frac{\frac{\mathcal{O}(A)}{\vdots}}{\Gamma, \alpha' \vdash \alpha'', \Delta} \quad \frac{\mathcal{O}(B)}{\vdots}}{\Gamma, \alpha' \vdash \beta, \Delta}$$

Let us now consider the second deduction, for again the first one is analogous. In this case, we get the desired possible deductions, applying the induction hypothesis of statement (3):

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\mathcal{O}(A')}{\vdots}}{\Gamma, \alpha' \vdash \Delta} \quad \frac{\mathcal{O}(B')}{\vdots}}{\Gamma, \alpha' \vdash \alpha'', \Delta} W_R \quad \frac{\mathcal{O}(B')}{\Gamma \vdash \beta, \Delta}}{\Gamma \vdash \alpha' \rightarrow \alpha'', \Delta} \rightarrow_R$$

If the last rule is \neg_R , then D is the deduction:

$$\frac{\frac{\mathcal{O}(D)}{\vdots}}{\Gamma, \alpha' \vdash \beta, \Delta}}{\Gamma \vdash \neg \alpha', \beta, \Delta} \neg_R$$

Applying the induction hypothesis of statement (3), we get one of these:

$$\frac{\frac{\mathcal{O}(A)}{\vdots}}{\Gamma, \alpha' \vdash \Delta} \quad \frac{\mathcal{O}(B)}{\vdots}}{\Gamma \vdash \beta, \Delta}}{\Gamma \vdash \neg \alpha', \Delta} \neg_R$$

If the last rule is either G_R , J_R or S_R , then $\Gamma, \Delta \subseteq \mathcal{E}$ and $\alpha, \beta \in \mathcal{E}$, say $\alpha = \rho$ and $\beta = \eta$. The shape of the deductions are these:

$$\frac{\frac{\overline{\rho \vdash \rho} \quad Ax \quad \frac{\mathcal{O}(D) \quad \vdots}{\Gamma \vdash \eta, \Delta}}{\Gamma \vdash \rho, \eta, \Delta} G_R \quad \frac{\mathcal{O}(D) \quad \vdots \quad \frac{\overline{\vdash \rho} \quad P_L}{\Gamma \vdash \rho, \eta, \Delta} J_R \quad \frac{\overline{\rho \vdash} \quad P_L \quad \frac{\mathcal{O}(D) \quad \vdots}{\Gamma \vdash \eta, \Delta}}{\Gamma \vdash \rho, \eta, \Delta} S_R$$

In any case, the induction hypothesis already gives a deduction B of $\Gamma \vdash \eta, \Delta$. To get $\Gamma \vdash \rho, \Delta$ we use P_R to get the deduction A of $\vdash \rho$ and then apply W_L and W_R . \dashv

Since we have all the apparatus at hand, let us take the opportunity to prove the admissibility of the contraction rules.

DEFINITION 3.2. *The contraction rules are the following rules:*

$$\frac{\Gamma, \alpha, \alpha \vdash \Delta}{\Gamma, \alpha \vdash \Delta} C_L \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash \alpha, \alpha, \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta} C_R$$

for every formula α and finite multisets of formulas Γ, Δ of \mathcal{F} .

THEOREM 3.1. *The contraction rules C_R and C_L are admissible in \mathcal{CP} .*

PROOF. If we have a postulative deduction:

$$\frac{\mathcal{O}(D) \quad \vdots \quad \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \alpha, \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta} C_R$$

We apply lemma 3.1 and obtain the following postulative deduction without contraction:

$$\frac{\mathcal{O}(D') \quad \vdots}{\Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta}$$

The same holds for C_L . For the case of an axiomatic deduction, since by theorem 2.1 \mathcal{CP} is a complete system for classical logic, we can use the regular deduction of the admissibility of contraction. \dashv

Now we are going to do the second, and main, step in the proof of the equivalence between consistency and satisfiability. For this, we extend the concept of compatibility to encompass valuations.

DEFINITION 3.3. *Let α be a formula. We say that an valuation $\phi : \mathcal{E}(\alpha) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ is compatible with a deduction D of α when, for every $\rho \in \mathcal{E}(\alpha)$, if $\phi(\rho) = 1$ then $\mathcal{O}(D)$ is positive or neutral about ρ and if $\phi(\rho) = 0$ then $\mathcal{O}(D)$ is negative or neutral about ρ . Analogously, a deduction D of α is said to be compatible with an valuation ϕ when, for every $\rho \in \mathcal{E}(\alpha)$, if $\mathcal{O}(D)$ is positive or*

Thus, define the valuation $\psi : \{\rho\} \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ such that $\psi(\rho) = 0$. For the converses in statements (1) and (2), we make the same reasoning as above but in backward direction.

We will continue in the same style: at first we think about the implications in statements (1) and (2), and then we analyse the sufficient changes in the steps in order to get their converses.

Suppose that α is a negation $\neg\beta$. A verification V of $\neg\beta$ must be

$$\begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(V) \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\beta \vdash}{\vdash \neg\beta} \neg_R \end{array}$$

because only \neg_R introduces a negation to the right. The induction hypothesis of statement (2) says that there is an valuation $\phi : \mathcal{E}(\beta) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ compatible with D such $\phi(\beta) = 0$, which means that $\phi(\neg\beta) = 1$. For a falsification F of $\neg\beta$, we make a dual reasoning, using the induction hypothesis of statement (1) to get an valuation $\phi : \mathcal{E}(\beta) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ compatible with F such $\phi(\beta) = 1$. For the converses, we reason in the same way but backward, using the induction hypotheses to obtain the postulative deductions of β compatible with the respective valuations.

Now we work on the case in which α is a conjunction $\beta \wedge \gamma$. A verification V of $\alpha \wedge \beta$ must be

$$\begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(V) \\ \vdots \quad \quad \quad \vdots \quad \quad \quad \vdots \\ \frac{\vdash \beta \quad \quad \quad \vdash \gamma}{\vdash \beta \wedge \gamma} \wedge_R \end{array}$$

because only \wedge_R introduces a conjunction to the right. From this, take the consistent subdeductions V_β and V_γ of V :

$$\begin{array}{cc} \mathcal{O}(V_\beta) & \mathcal{O}(V_\gamma) \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{}{\vdash \beta} & \frac{}{\vdash \gamma} \end{array}$$

The induction hypothesis ensures the existence of valuations $\phi_\beta : \mathcal{E}(\beta) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ such that $\phi_\beta(\beta) = 1$ and $\phi_\gamma : \mathcal{E}(\gamma) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ such that $\phi_\gamma(\gamma) = 1$. By proposition 2.1, every elementary formula in β occurs in $\mathcal{O}(V_\beta)$ and every elementary formula in γ occurs in $\mathcal{O}(V_\gamma)$. Since ϕ_β and ϕ_γ are compatible with V_β and V_γ , respectively, which are compatible with V and, by its turn, V is consistent, the union $\phi_\beta \cup \phi_\gamma$ is a well-defined valuation on $\mathcal{E}(\beta) \cup \mathcal{E}(\gamma)$ such that $\phi_\beta \cup \phi_\gamma(\beta \wedge \gamma) = 1$. For a falsification F of $\alpha \wedge \beta$, we know again it must be

$$\begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(F) \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\beta, \gamma \vdash}{\beta \wedge \gamma \vdash} \wedge_L \end{array}$$

By the statement (1) of lemma 3.1, there is a postulative deduction F_β of $\beta \vdash$ and there is a postulative deduction F_γ of $\gamma \vdash$, both compatible with F . From the induction hypothesis of statement (2), we know that there is an valuation $\psi_\beta : \mathcal{E}(\beta) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ such that $\psi_\beta(\beta) = 0$ and there is $\phi_\gamma : \mathcal{E}(\gamma) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ such that $\psi_\gamma(\gamma) = 0$, compatible respectively with F_β and F_γ . Proposition 2.1 ensures that every elementary formula in β occurs in $\mathcal{O}(F_\beta)$ and every elementary formula in γ occurs in $\mathcal{O}(F_\gamma)$. Since $\mathcal{O}(F)$ is consistent, we can define the valuation $\psi_{\beta,\gamma}$ on $\mathcal{E}(\beta) \cup \mathcal{E}(\gamma)$ such that $\psi_{\beta,\gamma}(\rho) = \psi_\beta(\rho)$ for $\rho \in \mathcal{E}(\beta)$ and $\psi_{\beta,\gamma}(\eta) = 1$ if $\mathcal{O}(F)$ is positive on η , otherwise $\psi_{\beta,\gamma}(\eta) = 0$ for $\eta \in \mathcal{E}(\gamma)$. Hence, it holds $\psi_{\beta,\gamma}(\beta \wedge \gamma) = 0$.

That is all for the implications in statements (1) and (2). For their converses, first, if we are faced with an valuation $\phi : \mathcal{E}(\beta) \cup \mathcal{E}(\gamma) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ such that $\phi(\beta \wedge \gamma) = 1$, we have postulative deductions V_β and V_γ of $\vdash \beta$ and $\vdash \gamma$, respectively, due to the induction hypothesis of statement (1) - and, of course: $\phi(\beta \wedge \gamma) = 1$ if, and only if, $\phi(\beta) = \phi(\gamma) = 1$. Moreover, by hypothesis ϕ , which is a function, is compatible with V_β and V_γ . Hence, $\mathcal{O}(V_\beta) \cup \mathcal{O}(V_\gamma)$ is a consistent foliage and the deduction bellow is the postulative deduction we are in need:

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(V_\beta) \\ \vdots \\ \vdash \beta \end{array} \quad \begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(V_\gamma) \\ \vdots \\ \vdash \gamma \end{array}}{\vdash \beta \wedge \gamma} \wedge_R$$

To finish the case for conjunction, we need to think from the hypothesis that there is an valuation $\psi : \mathcal{E}(\beta) \cup \mathcal{E}(\gamma) \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ such that $\psi(\beta \wedge \gamma) = 0$. In this case, $\psi(\beta) = 0$ or $\psi(\gamma) = 0$. If $\psi(\beta) = 0$, the induction hypothesis of statement (2) ensures that there is a postulative deduction F_β of $\beta \vdash$ compatible with ψ . This means that ψ is compatible with the following postulative deduction:

$$\frac{\begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(F_\beta) \\ \vdots \\ \beta \vdash \end{array} \quad W_L}{\beta, \gamma \vdash} \wedge_L$$

If $\psi(\gamma) = 0$, the reasoning is analogous. Therefore, the result is true for α a conjunction.

When α is a disjunction $\beta \vee \gamma$, the procedure is dual: we use W_R and statement (2) of lemma 3.1. With respect to α as an implication $\beta \rightarrow \gamma$, we also use the same strategy as for conjunction and disjunction, applying W_L and W_R and statement (3) of lemma 3.1. \dashv

Now we can end this section with the desired equivalence between consistency and satisfiability.

COROLLARY 3.1. *Consistency and satisfiability are equivalent.*

PROOF. For every formula α , α is consistent if, and only if, there is a verification V of α if, and only if, by the implication of statement (1) in theorem 3.2,

there is an valuation on $\mathcal{E}(\alpha)$ compatible with V that satisfies α . Thus, if α is consistent, there is an valuation that satisfies α . Similarly, the converse of statement (1) in theorem 3.2 shows that if α is satisfiable, then α is consistent. \dashv

§4. Cut rule admissibility and alternative systems. In this section we consider a possible alternative formulation for a sequent calculus, more in line with the usual structural rules about sequents. Before that, there is a task lacking in the analysis of the calculus \mathcal{CP} : to prove the cut rule admissibility. We do that now.

DEFINITION 4.1. *The cut rule is the following:*

$$\frac{\Gamma, \Gamma' \vdash \alpha, \Delta, \Delta' \quad \Gamma, \Gamma'' \vdash \Delta, \Delta''}{\Gamma, \Gamma', \Gamma'' \vdash \Delta, \Delta', \Delta''} \text{Cut}$$

for every formula α and every finite multisets of formulas $\Gamma, \Delta, \Gamma', \Gamma''$ and Δ', Δ'' of \mathcal{F} such that $\Gamma \cap \Gamma' = \Gamma \cap \Gamma'' = \Gamma' \cap \Gamma'' = \emptyset$ and $\Delta \cap \Delta' = \Delta \cap \Delta'' = \Delta' \cap \Delta'' = \emptyset$. The rule *Cut* also holds when there is no cut formula α ; in this case it just expresses the union of left and right contexts.

We explain below the reason for this exotic formulation of the cut rule. To save space, we write Γ'_Γ and Γ', Γ''_Γ instead of Γ, Γ' and $\Gamma, \Gamma', \Gamma''$.

THEOREM 4.1. *The rule Cut is admissible in CP.*

PROOF. We do an induction on the height h_D of an arbitrary deduction D that contains cut rules, with a subinduction on the composition of the cut formula α . The base case is $h_D = 2$, in which D has only one cut rule. In this case α is an elementary formula ρ . We also know that $\Gamma' = \Gamma'' = \Delta' = \Delta'' = \emptyset$ and $\Gamma = \Delta = \{\eta\}$ for some elementary formula η , because $\Gamma \vdash \rho, \Delta$ and $\Gamma, \rho \vdash \Delta$ must be the conclusion of P_L , P_R or Ax . Indeed, if $\Gamma = \Delta = \emptyset$, we could not apply cut, for the premises would be inconsistent. Therefore, the conclusion either is $\eta \vdash, \vdash \eta$ or $\eta \vdash \eta$, which we can get using P_L , P_R or Ax , respectively.

We assume that the cut rule already is admissible for $h_D \leq k$ as well as for the immediate subformulas of α in order to prove the result for $h_D = k + 1$ and α . In last cut rule applied in a deduction, there are three cases to be considered with respect to its left premise (by symmetry the same holds for the right one): (1) The cut formula is not principal in the left premise; (2) The cut formula is principal only in the left premise; (3) The cut formula is principal in both premises. In the cases (1) and (2), we show how to decrease the height of the last application of the cut rule to a deduction of height smaller than equal to k , but in the case (3) we are not be able to decrease the height of the last cut rule, and so we reduce the composition of the cut formula. We show below some representative applications of rules (displayed to the left) in these three cases, for the other rules the procedures of cut reduction (displayed to the right) are similar to the ones illustrated.

The case (1) means that the left premise was obtained by a left rule or a right rule. We analyze the left rules, for the right ones are dual. Below we display the cases for conjunction, disjunction and joint.

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\beta, \gamma, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha}{\beta \wedge \gamma, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha} \wedge_L \quad \frac{\alpha, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta}{\alpha, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta} \text{Cut} \\
\frac{\beta \wedge \gamma, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha}{\beta \wedge \gamma, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \Delta''_\Delta} \text{Cut}
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\beta, \gamma, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha \quad \alpha, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta}{\beta, \gamma, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \Delta''_\Delta} \text{Cut} \\
\frac{\beta, \gamma, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \Delta''_\Delta}{\beta \wedge \gamma, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \Delta''_\Delta} \wedge_L
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\beta, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha \quad \gamma, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha}{\beta \vee \gamma, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha} \vee_L \quad \frac{\alpha, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta}{\alpha, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta} \text{Cut} \\
\frac{\beta \vee \gamma, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha}{\beta \vee \gamma, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \Delta''_\Delta} \text{Cut}
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\beta, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha \quad \alpha, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta}{\beta, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \Delta''_\Delta} C \quad \frac{\gamma, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha \quad \alpha, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta}{\gamma, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \Delta''_\Delta} \text{Cut} \\
\frac{\beta, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \Delta''_\Delta \quad \gamma, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \Delta''_\Delta}{\beta \vee \gamma, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \Delta''_\Delta} \vee_L
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\vdash \rho \quad \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha}{\rho, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha} J_L \quad \frac{\alpha, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta}{\alpha, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta} \text{Cut} \\
\frac{\rho, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha}{\rho, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \Delta''_\Delta} \text{Cut}
\end{array}
\quad
\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha \quad \alpha, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta}{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \Delta''_\Delta} \text{Cut} \\
\frac{\rho \vdash \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \Delta''_\Delta}{\rho, \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \Delta''_\Delta} J_L
\end{array}$$

The case (2) means the right premise was obtained by a left rule or right rule. Below we exhibit the cases for negation, implication and merge to right rules.

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\alpha, \Gamma''_1, \beta \vdash \Delta''_\Delta}{\alpha, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \neg \beta, \Delta''_\Delta} \neg_R \quad \frac{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha \quad \alpha, \Gamma''_1, \beta \vdash \Delta''_\Delta}{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha} \text{Cut} \\
\frac{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha \quad \alpha, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \neg \beta, \Delta''_\Delta}{\Gamma', \Gamma''_1 \vdash \neg \beta, \Delta', \Delta''_\Delta} \text{Cut} \quad \frac{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha \quad \alpha, \Gamma''_1, \beta \vdash \Delta''_\Delta}{\Gamma', \Gamma''_1 \vdash \neg \beta, \Delta', \Delta''_\Delta} \neg_R
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\alpha, \Gamma''_1, \beta \vdash \gamma, \Delta''_\Delta}{\alpha, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \beta \rightarrow \gamma, \Delta''_\Delta} \rightarrow_R \quad \frac{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha \quad \alpha, \Gamma''_1, \beta \vdash \gamma, \Delta''_\Delta}{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha} \text{Cut} \\
\frac{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha \quad \alpha, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \beta \rightarrow \gamma, \Delta''_\Delta}{\Gamma', \Gamma''_1 \vdash \beta \rightarrow \gamma, \Delta', \Delta''_\Delta} \text{Cut} \quad \frac{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha \quad \alpha, \Gamma''_1, \beta \vdash \gamma, \Delta''_\Delta}{\Gamma', \Gamma''_1 \vdash \beta \rightarrow \gamma, \Delta', \Delta''_\Delta} \rightarrow_R
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\alpha, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta \quad \rho \vdash \rho}{\alpha, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta, \rho} G_R \quad \frac{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha \quad \alpha, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta}{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha} \text{Cut} \\
\frac{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha \quad \alpha, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta, \rho}{\Gamma', \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta', \Delta''_\Delta, \rho} \text{Cut} \quad \frac{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \alpha \quad \alpha, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta}{\Gamma', \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta', \Delta''_\Delta, \rho} G_R
\end{array}$$

The case (3) means the left premise was obtained by a right rule and the right premise by a left rule. Note that there is a peculiarity of the sequent calculus in this case: we cannot have applied joint and cross rules on both sides because this would make the foliage inconsistent.

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\rho \vdash \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta}{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \rho} S_R \quad \frac{\rho \vdash \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta}{\rho, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta} J_L \\
\frac{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \rho \quad \rho, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta}{\Gamma', \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta', \Delta''_\Delta} \text{Cut} \quad \frac{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta \quad \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta}{\Gamma', \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta', \Delta''_\Delta} \text{Cut}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\Gamma'_1, \beta \vdash \Delta'_\Delta}{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \neg \beta, \Delta'_\Delta} \neg_R \quad \frac{\Gamma''_1 \vdash \beta, \Delta''_\Delta}{\Gamma''_1 \vdash \neg \beta, \Delta''_\Delta} \neg_L \\
\frac{\Gamma'_1, \beta \vdash \Delta'_\Delta \quad \Gamma''_1 \vdash \beta, \Delta''_\Delta}{\Gamma', \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta', \Delta''_\Delta} \text{Cut} \quad \frac{\Gamma'_1, \beta \vdash \Delta'_\Delta \quad \Gamma'_1 \vdash \beta, \Delta'_\Delta}{\Gamma', \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta', \Delta''_\Delta} \text{Cut}
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{c}
\frac{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \beta \quad \Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \gamma}{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \beta \wedge \gamma} \wedge_R \quad \frac{\beta, \gamma, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta}{\beta \wedge \gamma, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta} \wedge_L \\
\frac{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \beta \wedge \gamma \quad \beta, \gamma, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta}{\Gamma', \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta', \Delta''_\Delta} \text{Cut} \quad \frac{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \beta \quad \beta, \gamma, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta}{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \gamma} \text{Cut} \\
\frac{\Gamma'_1 \vdash \Delta'_\Delta, \gamma \quad \gamma, \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta''_\Delta}{\Gamma', \Gamma''_1 \vdash \Delta', \Delta''_\Delta} \text{Cut}
\end{array}$$

In the reductions above we use the subinduction hypothesis because the height h_D is not reduced (we applied two times the cut rule in the last instance). \dashv

Differently from the regular proofs of cut admissibility or elimination, we have made a direct proof by induction on the height of the deductions, using a new trick: in the rule Cut contexts of the premises are partially shared. For this reason it is not necessary to make contractions in the conclusion of the reduced cut. However, the regular rule Cut^* does not share contexts:

$$\frac{\Gamma' \vdash \alpha, \Delta' \quad \Gamma'', \alpha \vdash \Delta''}{\Gamma', \Gamma'' \vdash \Delta', \Delta''} Cut^*$$

Are we loosing something? Fortunately, no. The rule Cut^* is derivable from our restrict rule Cut . To believe in it, contemplate the following reasoning. Suppose that $\Gamma = \Gamma' \cap \Gamma''$ and $\Delta = \Delta' \cap \Delta''$. Then $\Gamma' = \Gamma' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma$ and $\Gamma'' = \Gamma'' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma$. The same holds for Δ' and Δ'' . Hence,

$$\begin{array}{c} \frac{\frac{\frac{\Gamma' \vdash \alpha, \Delta'}{\vdots W_L} \quad \frac{\Gamma'', \alpha \vdash \Delta''}{\vdots W_L}}{\Gamma', \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta'} \quad \frac{\frac{\Gamma'', \alpha \vdash \Delta''}{\vdots W_L} \quad \frac{\Gamma', \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta'}{\vdots W_R}}{\Gamma'', \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta''}}{\Gamma', \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta', \Delta} \quad \frac{\frac{\Gamma'', \alpha \vdash \Delta''}{\vdots W_L} \quad \frac{\Gamma', \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta'}{\vdots W_R}}{\Gamma'', \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta'', \Delta}}{\vdots C_L} \quad \frac{\frac{\Gamma'', \alpha \vdash \Delta''}{\vdots W_L} \quad \frac{\Gamma', \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta'}{\vdots W_R}}{\Gamma'', \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta'', \Delta}}{\vdots C_L} \\ \frac{\frac{\frac{\Gamma' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta', \Delta}{\vdots C_L} \quad \frac{\Gamma'', \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta'', \Delta}{\vdots C_L}}{\Gamma' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta', \Delta} \quad \frac{\frac{\Gamma'', \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta'', \Delta}{\vdots C_L} \quad \frac{\Gamma' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta', \Delta}{\vdots C_L}}{\Gamma'' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta'', \Delta}}{\vdots C_R} \quad \frac{\frac{\Gamma' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta', \Delta}{\vdots C_L} \quad \frac{\Gamma'', \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta'', \Delta}{\vdots C_L}}{\Gamma' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta', \Delta} \quad \frac{\frac{\Gamma'', \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta'', \Delta}{\vdots C_L} \quad \frac{\Gamma' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta', \Delta}{\vdots C_L}}{\Gamma'' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta'', \Delta}}{\vdots C_R} \\ \frac{\frac{\frac{\Gamma' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta', \Delta}{\vdots C_R} \quad \frac{\Gamma'' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta'', \Delta}{\vdots C_R}}{\Gamma' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma'' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma \vdash \Delta' \setminus \Delta, \Delta'' \setminus \Delta, \Delta} \quad \frac{\frac{\Gamma' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta', \Delta}{\vdots C_R} \quad \frac{\Gamma'' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma \vdash \alpha, \Delta'', \Delta}{\vdots C_R}}{\Gamma' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma'' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma \vdash \Delta' \setminus \Delta, \Delta'' \setminus \Delta, \Delta}}{Cut} \\ \frac{\frac{\frac{\Gamma' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma, \Gamma'' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma \vdash \Delta' \setminus \Delta, \Delta'' \setminus \Delta, \Delta}{\vdots W_L}}{\Gamma' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma, \Gamma'' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma \vdash \Delta' \setminus \Delta, \Delta'' \setminus \Delta, \Delta}}{\vdots W_R} \\ \frac{\frac{\Gamma' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma, \Gamma'' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma \vdash \Delta' \setminus \Delta, \Delta'' \setminus \Delta, \Delta}{\vdots W_R}}{\Gamma' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma, \Gamma'' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma \vdash \Delta' \setminus \Delta, \Delta'' \setminus \Delta, \Delta}}{R=} \\ \frac{\Gamma' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma'' \setminus \Gamma, \Gamma \vdash \Delta', \Delta''}{R=}$$

where the notation for W_L, W_R, C_L, C_R means that we applied these rules many times to get the new contexts, and the notion $R_=$ indicates, of course, that both sequents are equal as multisets. This shows that Cut^* is admissible in a calculus with Cut , which, by its turn, is admissible in \mathcal{CP} , as desired. Since the admissibility of cut ensures, by pure syntactic means, that the calculus \mathcal{CP} is consistent, we can now turn to new ones.

The alternative calculus to be studied here uses weakening and cut restricted to elementary formulas. This formulation is interesting because it shows a different perspective to the regular structural rules in the context of double sequents. Moreover, it is a calculus with rules similar to the ones used in regular presentations of sequent calculae.

DEFINITION 4.2. *The system \mathcal{CP}^* has the rules \mathcal{CP} minus the joint and cross rules plus two new pairs of postulative rules. The first is called restricted weakening rules:*

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \Delta}{\Gamma, \rho \vdash \Delta} W_L^* \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \rho, \Delta} W_R^*$$

the second is the restricted cut rules:

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \rho, \Delta \quad \rho \vdash}{\Gamma \vdash \Delta} Cut_L \quad \frac{\vdash \rho \quad \Gamma, \rho \vdash \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \Delta} Cut_R$$

where $\Gamma, \Delta \subseteq \mathcal{E}$ and $\rho \in \mathcal{E}$ with Γ and Δ finite multisets.

The example bellow illustrates how some deductions of system \mathcal{CP} can be simulated in system \mathcal{CP}^* .

EXAMPLE 4.1. *In the system \mathcal{CP}^* we can make the following verifications for a disjunction $\rho \vee \eta$:*

$$\begin{array}{ccc} \frac{\frac{\frac{\overline{\vdash \eta} P_R}{\vdash \eta} \quad \frac{\frac{\overline{\vdash \rho} P_R}{\vdash \rho} W_L^*}{\eta \vdash \rho} Cut_R}{\vdash \rho, \eta} W_R^*}{\vdash \rho, \eta} \vee_R}{\vdash \rho \vee \eta} & \frac{\frac{\frac{\overline{\vdash \rho} P_R}{\vdash \rho, \eta} W_R^* \quad \frac{\overline{\eta \vdash} P_L}{\eta \vdash} Cut_L}{\vdash \rho, \eta} W_R^*}{\vdash \rho, \eta} \vee_R}{\vdash \rho \vee \eta} & \frac{\frac{\frac{\frac{\overline{\vdash \eta} P_R}{\vdash \rho, \eta} W_R^* \quad \frac{\overline{\rho \vdash} P_L}{\rho \vdash} Cut_L}{\vdash \rho, \eta} W_R^*}{\vdash \rho, \eta} \vee_R}{\vdash \rho \vee \eta} \end{array}$$

The procedure in example 4.1 can be extended to every postulative deduction.

LEMMA 4.1. *Every postulative deduction D in \mathcal{CP} can be transformed into a postulative deduction D^* of \mathcal{CP}^* such that D and D^* are compatible to each other.*

PROOF. It is sufficient to show that every subdeduction D of a stem $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$ in a postulative deduction obtained in \mathcal{CP} can be transformed into a postulative deduction D^* in \mathcal{CP}^* , because the part of the deduction with the rules for connectives does not change. Since $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$ is a stem, we know that $\Gamma, \Delta \subseteq \mathcal{E}$, say $\Gamma = \{\rho_1, \dots, \rho_m\}$ and $\Delta = \{\eta_1, \dots, \eta_n\}$. We build a sequence of sequents $\Gamma_1 \vdash \Delta_1, \dots, \Gamma_{m+n} \vdash \Delta_{m+n}$ in a postulative deduction D^* in \mathcal{CP}^* such that $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$ is $\Gamma_{m+n} \vdash \Delta_{m+n}$. Take the first elementary formula η in Δ for which D is positive on it. Thus, $\Gamma_1 \vdash \Delta_1$ is the deduction

$$\frac{\overline{\vdash \eta} P_R}{\vdash \eta}$$

If there is no η in Δ for which D is positive on it, this means that all elementary formulas in Δ were introduced in D with S_R . Hence, there is the first ρ in Γ for which D is negative on it, because Γ has only elementary formulas to the left and at least one of them was introduced with P_L . In this case, $\Gamma_1 \vdash \Delta_1$ is the deduction

$$\frac{\overline{\rho \vdash} P_L}{\rho \vdash}$$

We build $\Gamma_i \vdash \Delta_i$ as the conclusion of a deduction from $\Gamma_{i-1} \vdash \Delta_{i-1}$, for $1 < i \leq m+n$, in this way:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\mathcal{O}(D') \\
\vdots \\
\frac{\Gamma' \vdash \Delta'}{\Gamma' \vdash \rho, \Delta'} W_R \\
\vdots \\
\frac{}{\Gamma \vdash \rho, \Delta}
\end{array}$$

This is so because \mathcal{CP}^* only has the rule W_R^* to introduce an elementary formula to the right in postulative deduction like D' that does not have cuts (the ρ to the right was not introduced by Ax because D' is postulative). Consider D'' equals to D' but without this W_R^* that introduced ρ to the right. Hence, D'' is compatible with D and has conclusion $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$. \dashv

THEOREM 4.2. *For every formula α , α is consistent in the system \mathcal{CP}^* without the restricted cut rules Cut_L and Cut_R if, and only if, α is satisfiable.*

PROOF. Let \mathcal{CP}^{**} be the system \mathcal{CP}^* minus the rules Cut_L and Cut_R . Suppose that α is consistent in D^{**} , i.e. there is a verification D^{**} of α in \mathcal{CP}^{**} . Each stem $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$ in the stem decomposition $\mathcal{T}(D^{**})$ can be prove in \mathcal{CP} preserving compatibility. Indeed, assume that $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$ in $\mathcal{T}(D^{**})$ is such that $\Gamma = \{\rho_1, \dots, \rho_m\}$ and $\Delta = \{\eta_1, \dots, \eta_n\}$. We build a postulative deduction D in \mathcal{CP} of $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$ compatible with D^{**} as in the proof of lemma 4.1, but following the procedure bellow:

- (1) Begin D with $\vdash \eta$, and so using P_R , where η is the first $\eta \in \Delta$ for which D^{**} is positive on η . If there is no such a η , begin D with the first ρ for which D^{**} is negative on ρ , and so using P_L .
- (2) For each $\eta_j \in \Delta \setminus \Gamma$, if D^{**} is not negative on η_j , extend D by doing the following:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\mathcal{O}(D) \\
\vdots \\
\frac{\frac{}{\Gamma_{j-1} \vdash \Delta_{j-1}} \quad \frac{}{\vdash \eta_j} P_R}{\Gamma_{j-1} \vdash \Delta_{j-1}, \eta_j} J_R
\end{array}$$

- (3) For each $\eta_j \in \Delta \cap \Gamma$, if D^{**} is not negative on η_j , extend D by doing the following:

$$\begin{array}{c}
\mathcal{O}(D) \\
\vdots \\
\frac{\frac{\frac{}{\Gamma_{j-1} \vdash \Delta_{j-1}} \quad \frac{}{\vdash \eta_j} P_R}{\eta_j, \Gamma_{j-1} \vdash \Delta_{j-1}} S_L \quad \frac{}{\vdash \eta_j} P_R}{\eta_j, \Gamma_{j-1} \vdash \Delta_{j-1}, \eta_j} J_R
\end{array}$$

- (4) For each $\rho_i \in \Gamma \setminus \Delta$, if D^{**} is not positive on ρ_i , extend D by doing the following:

$$\frac{\frac{\rho_i \vdash \quad P_L}{\rho_i \vdash} \quad \frac{\mathcal{O}(D) \quad \vdots}{\Gamma_{i-1} \vdash \Delta_{i-1}}}{\rho_i, \Gamma_{i-1} \vdash \Delta_{i-1}} J_L$$

- (5) For each $\rho_i \in \Gamma \cap \Delta$, if D^{**} is not positive on ρ_i and ρ_i was not already introduced in D in the step (3), then extend D by doing the following:

$$\frac{\frac{\rho_i \vdash \quad P_L}{\rho_i \vdash} \quad \frac{\frac{\rho_i \vdash \quad P_L}{\rho_i \vdash} \quad \frac{\mathcal{O}(D) \quad \vdots}{\Gamma_{i-1} \vdash \Delta_{i-1}}}{\Gamma_{i-1} \vdash \Delta_{i-1}, \rho_i} S_R}{\rho_i, \Gamma_{i-1} \vdash \Delta_{i-1}, \rho_i} J_L$$

This procedure ensures that D is a verification in \mathcal{CP} of $\Gamma \vdash \Delta$ compatible with D^{**} . By theorem 3.2, α is satisfiable.

Conversely, suppose that α is satisfiable. By theorem 3.2, there is a verification of α in \mathcal{CP} . By lemma 4.1, D can be transformed into a postulative deduction D^* of \mathcal{CP}^* such that D^* is compatible with D . By lemma 4.2 the rules Cut_L and Cut_R can be eliminated from \mathcal{CP}^* . Therefore, there is a verification of α in the system \mathcal{CP}^{**} . \dashv

Although we can prove that the weakening rules W_L and W_R are admissible in \mathcal{CP}^* , using a method similar to that presented here for \mathcal{CP} , the restricted weakening rules W_L^* and W_R^* are clearly not eliminable. For instance, we cannot prove $\vdash \rho \vee \eta$ from $\vdash \rho$ or $\vdash \eta$ without W_R^* in \mathcal{CP}^* . In a sense, the system \mathcal{CP}^* without restricted cut rules is the minimal system that is able to represent satisfiability. Nevertheless, the proof of theorem 4.2 shows that this minimality has a cost: we lose the syntactic representation of the valuations in the foliages of the postulative deductions. This explains why the calculus \mathcal{CP} has the rules for joint, cross and merge. These rules make an explicit representation of the model associated to the formulas in the foliage of postulative deductions. The calculus \mathcal{CP} has a direct and internal representation of satisfiability and the proof of theorem 4.2 shows why its rules are not arbitrary.

§5. Rule extensions. We now turn our attention to the possibility of extension of a system for classical propositional logic with nonlogical rules. This kind of approach was developed in [21] and [15] and extensively study by Negri & von Plato in [17]. The idea is to make extensions with nonlogical rules that correspond to formulas that represent stems. More precisely, given a stem $\rho_1, \dots, \rho_m \vdash \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n$ in the stem decomposition of a deduction of α , the *stem formula* associated to this stem is the disjunction $\neg\rho_1 \vee \dots \vee \neg\rho_m \vee \eta_1 \vee \dots \vee \eta_n$, which is equivalent to $\rho_1 \wedge \dots \wedge \rho_m \rightarrow \eta_1 \vee \dots \vee \eta_n$. We know that a formula α is equivalent to the conjunction of its stem formulas in a deduction, it does matter which one [16][p.51]. Hence, we can add rules that represent α via its stem formulas.

DEFINITION 5.1. *Given a calculus \mathcal{C} and a formula α , the α -rule extension of \mathcal{C} is the calculus $\mathcal{C} \cup \{R_1^\alpha\} \cdots \cup \{R_n^\alpha\}$ where each R_i^α is the α -rule*

$$\frac{\zeta_1, \Gamma \vdash \Delta \quad \cdots \quad \zeta_n, \Gamma \vdash \Delta}{\xi_1, \dots, \xi_m, \Gamma \vdash \Delta} R_i^\alpha$$

associated to each stem formula $\xi_1 \wedge \cdots \wedge \xi_m \rightarrow \zeta_1 \vee \cdots \vee \zeta_n$ of the stem decomposition $\mathcal{T}(D)$ for some deduction D of α .

In [15], Negri & vonPlato showed that to extend an intuitionistic sequent calculus (*G3im*) with α -rules is equivalent to extend it with α as a nonlogical axiom. Negri & vonPlato also claimed that rule extensions can be made for a sequent calculus for classical propositional logic, but they did not provide a proof. We show here that this is not exactly correct, because there is a limitation generated by the Post-completeness of classical propositional logic. We begin with the definition of a general notion of rule extension, beyond α -rules.

DEFINITION 5.2. *An elementary rule is either a rule R_L or R_R of the form*

$$\frac{\Upsilon_1, \Gamma \vdash \Delta \quad \cdots \quad \Upsilon_n, \Gamma \vdash \Delta}{\Upsilon, \Gamma \vdash \Delta} R_L \quad \frac{\Gamma \vdash \Delta, \Lambda_1 \quad \cdots \quad \Gamma \vdash \Delta, \Lambda_n}{\Gamma \vdash \Delta, \Lambda} R_R$$

where each Υ_i , Λ_i as well as Υ and Λ is a multisets of elementary formulas (maybe some of them are actually empty). The formulas in $\Upsilon_1, \dots, \Upsilon_n$ and $\Lambda_1, \dots, \Lambda_n$ are the principal formulas of R_L and R_R , respectively. A sequent calculus \mathcal{C}' is a rule extension of a sequent calculus \mathcal{C} if \mathcal{C}' has all the rules of \mathcal{C} plus some elementary rules; we say that \mathcal{C}' is conservative if all admissible rules of \mathcal{C} are also admissible in \mathcal{C}' . A calculus \mathcal{C} is consistent if there no β such that β and $\neg\beta$ are provable in $\mathcal{S}(\mathcal{C})$, otherwise, it is inconsistent.

Note that α -rule extensions are a particular case of rule extensions, namely, rule extensions made with left elementary rules associated to the stem decomposition of a formula. Besides, right elementary rules can also be used to make extensions associated to the stem decomposition of a formula. Explicitly, this could be done with rules of the form

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \Delta, \xi_1 \quad \cdots \quad \Gamma \vdash \Delta, \xi_m}{\Gamma \vdash \Delta, \zeta_1, \dots, \zeta_n} \alpha_R$$

associated to the formula $\xi_1 \wedge \cdots \wedge \xi_m \rightarrow \zeta_1 \vee \cdots \vee \zeta_n$. Thus, rule extensions are just a generalization of Negri & vonPlato's approach to a possible classical context, which, as we are going to show now, requires sequent calculus to be consistently made.

We provide a different version of Hilbert & Ackermann's proof of the mentioned Post-completeness [2][p.42], adapted here to \mathcal{CP} . There is nothing peculiar to the calculus \mathcal{CP} , the proof can be adapted to any other sequent calculus sound and complete for classical propositional logic. It is important to emphasize, however, that such an adaptation may not be simple. Indeed, we need to make some formal definitions and explicitly exhibit assumptions in Hilbert & Ackermann's

original proof made for an axiomatic system, and this resulted in a quite different proof.

DEFINITION 5.3. *The elementary substitution rule is the following*

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \Delta}{\Gamma[\neg\rho/\rho] \vdash \Delta[\neg\rho/\rho]} \text{ Sub}$$

where $\Gamma[\neg\rho/\rho]$ and $\Delta[\neg\rho/\rho]$ means that $\neg\rho$ is substitute for ρ in all formulas of Γ and Δ , respectively.

LEMMA 5.1. *Elementary substitution is admissible in \mathcal{CP} .*

PROOF. Consider the following axiomatic deduction D in \mathcal{CP} :

$$\begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(D) \\ \vdots \\ \hline \Gamma \vdash \Delta \end{array}$$

We substitute $\neg\rho$ for ρ in all sequents of D from the root up to, but not including, each stem in D . Now, we take each stem $\rho_1, \dots, \rho_m \vdash \eta_1, \dots, \eta_n$ in D , substitute $\neg\rho$ for ρ and do the following for each $\rho_i = \rho$ and each $\eta_i = \rho$:

$$\frac{\frac{\Gamma, \rho_i \vdash \rho_i, \Delta}{\Gamma, \rho_i, \neg\rho_i \vdash \Delta} \neg_L}{\Gamma, \neg\rho_i \vdash \neg\rho_i, \Delta} \neg_R \quad \frac{\frac{\Gamma', \eta_i \vdash \eta_i, \Delta'}{\Gamma', \eta_i, \neg\eta_i \vdash \Delta'} \neg_L}{\Gamma', \neg\eta_i \vdash \neg\eta_i, \Delta'} \neg_R$$

where $\Gamma, \Delta, \Gamma', \Delta'$ are the other elements in the stem different from ρ_i and η_i . Let us denote this new deduction D' . We have that D' has the following shape:

$$\begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(D') \\ \vdots \\ \hline \Gamma[\neg\rho/\rho] \vdash \Delta[\neg\rho/\rho] \end{array}$$

Moreover, D' has the same connective rules of D expect the rules \neg_L and \neg_R indicated above, $\mathcal{T}(D') = \mathcal{T}(D)$ and, actually, the limbs of D' are equal to the limbs of D . Therefore, D' is an axiomatic deduction in \mathcal{CP} of $\Gamma[\neg\rho/\rho] \vdash \Delta[\neg\rho/\rho]$. \dashv

DEFINITION 5.4. *A sequent calculus \mathcal{C} is Post-complete when, for every formula α in \mathcal{F} such that α is not provable in \mathcal{C} , we have that, for every conservative rule extension \mathcal{C}' of \mathcal{C} , if α is provable in \mathcal{C}' , then \mathcal{C}' is inconsistent.*

THEOREM 5.1. *\mathcal{CP} is Post-complete.*

PROOF. Take a formula α that is not provable in \mathcal{CP} . Let \mathcal{CP}^α be a conservative rule extension of \mathcal{CP} in which α is provable. If α is an elementary formula ρ , the lemma 5.1 already gives us a proof of $\neg\rho$, and thus \mathcal{CP}^α is inconsistent. For the case α is a composed formula, we know that it is equivalent to the conjunction $\beta_1 \wedge \dots \wedge \beta_k$ of the formulas associated to the stems in $\mathcal{T}(D)$ [16][p.51]. Given that α is non-provable in \mathcal{CP} , take the first β_i that is non-provable too.

Due to the associativity of disjunction, we can consider β_i to be $\xi_1 \vee \dots \vee \xi_n$, where each ξ_i is a literal. If one of these literals, say ξ_i , is provable in \mathcal{CP}^α , then we just apply lemma 5.1 to get a new axiomatic deduction of $\neg\xi_i$, which means that the system \mathcal{CP}^α is inconsistent. If all of ξ_1, \dots, ξ_n was not provable, then β_i itself ought be provable in \mathcal{CP}^α because α is provable in \mathcal{CP}^α . Let us think that D is such an axiomatic deduction. Without lost of generality, we may assume that the first literals ξ_1, \dots, ξ_k are actually negations of elementary formulas, i.e., for each $1 \leq i \leq k$, $\xi_i = \neg\bar{\xi}_i$, and all the remain ξ_{k+1}, \dots, ξ_n are elementary formulas. If all of them are just elementary formulas, the proof is analogous. Since \mathcal{CP}^α is a rule extension of \mathcal{CP} , in order to get $\xi_1 \vee \dots \vee \xi_n$, the deduction D must have steps of the form

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \xi_i, \xi_j, \Delta, \Phi}{\Gamma \vdash \xi_i \vee \xi_j, \Delta, \Phi}$$

where $\Gamma \subseteq \{\bar{\xi}_1, \dots, \bar{\xi}_k\}$, $\Delta \subseteq \{\xi_{k+1}, \dots, \xi_n\}$ and Φ is a multiset of disjunctions of some of the literals ξ_1, \dots, ξ_k . For the same reason, D must also have steps of the form

$$\frac{\bar{\xi}_i, \Gamma \vdash \Delta, \Phi}{\Gamma \vdash \neg\bar{\xi}_i, \Delta, \Phi}$$

So that at the bottom, D has an application of \vee_R ; something like this

$$\begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(D) \\ \vdots \\ \frac{}{\vdash \xi_1 \vee \dots \vee \xi_n} \vee_R \end{array}$$

From up-down, because D must have only axioms in its foliage $\mathcal{O}(D)$, we know that D must also have some application of a left or right elementary rule with the shape

$$\frac{\zeta_1 \vdash \zeta_1 \quad \dots \quad \zeta_p \vdash \zeta_p}{\Gamma \vdash} R_L \qquad \frac{\zeta_1 \vdash \zeta_1 \quad \dots \quad \zeta_p \vdash \zeta_p}{\vdash \Delta} R_R$$

We consider the right case, for the left one is just the dual. For simplicity, let us suppose that $\Delta = \xi_{k+1}, \dots, \xi_n$. By the admissibility of elementary substitution (lemma 5.1) and cut (theorem 4.1), we can do in \mathcal{CP}^α :

$$\frac{\frac{\zeta_1 \vdash \zeta_1 \quad \dots \quad \zeta_p \vdash \zeta_p}{\vdash \xi_{k+1}, \dots, \xi_n} R_R \quad \frac{\zeta_1 \vdash \zeta_1 \quad \dots \quad \zeta_p \vdash \zeta_p}{\vdash \Delta} R_R}{\frac{\neg\xi_{k+1} \vdash \xi_{k+2}, \dots, \xi_n}{\vdash \xi_{k+2}, \dots, \xi_n} \neg_L \quad \frac{\vdash \Delta}{\vdash \Delta[\neg\xi_{k+1}/\xi_{k+1}]} Sub} Cut$$

If ξ_{k+1} has more than one occurrence in Δ , we apply contractions on both branches until we get just one occurrence of ξ_{k+1} before to apply \neg_L and Sub above. By theorem 3.1, contractions rules are admissible in \mathcal{CP}^α . As our cut rule

partially shares the contexts 4.1, we can repeat this procedure on ξ_{k+2}, \dots, ξ_n until we get an axiomatic deduction

$$\begin{array}{c} \mathcal{O}(E) \\ \vdots \\ \hline \vdash \xi_n \end{array}$$

Finally, we apply elementary substitution on the conclusion of E and verify that the system \mathcal{CP}^α is inconsistent in this case as well. \dashv

COROLLARY 5.1. *There is no consistent α -rule extension of \mathcal{CP} for α non-provable in \mathcal{CP} .*

PROOF. Let α be non-provable in \mathcal{CP} . Consider \mathcal{C}^α an α -rule extension of \mathcal{C} . Take the rule R_i^α in \mathcal{C}^α :

$$\frac{\zeta_1, \Gamma \vdash \Delta \quad \dots \quad \zeta_n, \Gamma \vdash \Delta}{\xi_1, \dots, \xi_m, \Gamma \vdash \Delta} R_i^\alpha$$

Consider $\Gamma = \emptyset$ and $\Delta = \{\zeta_1, \dots, \zeta_n\}$, we can make the following deduction in \mathcal{C}^α :

$$\begin{array}{c} \zeta_1 \vdash \zeta_1 \qquad \qquad \zeta_n \vdash \zeta_n \\ \vdots W_R \qquad \qquad \qquad \vdots W_R \\ \hline \zeta_1 \vdash \zeta_1, \dots, \zeta_n \quad \dots \quad \zeta_n \vdash \zeta_1, \dots, \zeta_n \\ \hline \xi_1, \dots, \xi_m \vdash \zeta_1, \dots, \zeta_n \\ \xi_1 \wedge \xi_2, \dots, \xi_m \vdash \zeta_1, \dots, \zeta_n \quad \wedge_L \\ \vdots \\ \xi_1 \wedge \dots \wedge \xi_m \vdash \zeta_1, \dots, \zeta_n \quad \wedge_L \\ \xi_1 \wedge \dots \wedge \xi_m \vdash \zeta_1 \vee \zeta_2, \dots, \zeta_n \quad \vee_R \\ \vdots \\ \xi_1 \wedge \dots \wedge \xi_m \vdash \zeta_1 \vee \dots \vee \zeta_n \quad \vee_R \\ \hline \vdash \xi_1 \wedge \dots \wedge \xi_m \rightarrow \zeta_1 \vee \dots \vee \zeta_n \quad \rightarrow_R \end{array} R_i^\alpha$$

This deduction D_i is an axiomatic deduction in \mathcal{CP}^α . Now take the deductions D_1, \dots, D_n that deduce each stem formula in the stem decomposition of α . By applying \wedge_R in the conclusions of these deductions, we get an axiomatic deduction of a formula α^* equivalent to α in \mathcal{CP}^α . This means that α^* is non-provable in \mathcal{CP} . Therefore, by the Post-completeness of \mathcal{CP} , we conclude that \mathcal{CP}^α is inconsistent. \dashv

To clarify what is going on, consider the next example.

EXAMPLE 5.1. *Suppose we want to add a non-logical rule for the formula $p \vee p$ in the system \mathcal{CP} . Using a left elementary rule, we must be have*

$$\frac{p, \Gamma \vdash \Delta \quad p, \Gamma \vdash \Delta}{\Gamma \vdash \Delta} L_{p \vee p}$$

Let us denote \mathcal{CP}^* the system \mathcal{CP} with this rule added to its calculus. We can do the following axiomatic deduction of p in \mathcal{CP}^* :

$$\frac{\frac{\text{---}}{p \vdash p} Ax \quad \frac{\text{---}}{p \vdash p} Ax}{\vdash p} L_{p \vee p}$$

Since elementary substitution must hold for \mathcal{CP}^* , otherwise it is not a conservative extension of \mathcal{CP} , then we also must have an appropriate axiomatic deduction with the same conclusion like this:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\text{---}}{p \vdash p} Ax}{p, \neg p \vdash} \neg_L \quad \frac{\frac{\text{---}}{p \vdash p} Ax}{p, \neg p \vdash} \neg_L}{\neg p \vdash \neg p} \neg_R \quad \frac{\frac{\text{---}}{p \vdash p} Ax}{p, \neg p \vdash} \neg_L \quad \frac{\frac{\text{---}}{p \vdash p} Ax}{p, \neg p \vdash} \neg_L}{\neg p \vdash \neg p} R}{\vdash \neg p}$$

Nonetheless, such a deduction needs to be in a format that uses only left or right elementary non-logical rule. A possible right elementary rule added to \mathcal{CP}^* may be

$$\frac{\Gamma \vdash \Delta, p \quad \Gamma \vdash \Delta, p}{\Gamma \vdash \Delta} R_{p \wedge p}$$

Given such a rule, it is possible to do in \mathcal{CP}^* the following deduction:

$$\frac{\frac{\frac{\text{---}}{p \vdash p} Ax \quad \frac{\text{---}}{p \vdash p} Ax}{p \vdash} R_{p \wedge p}}{\vdash \neg p} \neg_R$$

Hence, the system \mathcal{CP}^* is actually inconsistent.

As we can see in the proof of the Post-completeness of \mathcal{CP} above, the problem with rule extensions is that they are incompatible with elementary substitution. This property is a cornerstone for classical propositional logic. Although we have presented it here as a syntactic property, elementary substitution is intrinsic to the bi-valued semantics of the classical connectives. If α is a tautology, i.e., all the rows of a truth-table for a formula α attributes the value *true* to α , this value will not change if we change the values of the propositional variables of α in the truth-table; α will continue to be a tautology. For this reason, Hilbert & Ackermann assumed elementary substitution as a logical axiom in their axiomatic system [2][p.27]⁴.

Fortunately, the proof of corollary 5.1 exhibits a way to get consistent rule extensions of classical propositional logic, namely, rule extensions cannot provide new axiomatic deductions beyond those already given in the system \mathcal{CP} . This amounts to making the restriction that $\{\zeta_i\} \cup \Gamma \cap \Delta = \emptyset$ for each i in each α -rule. As we can see in the proof of corollary 5.1, this means that α -rules will provide new postulative deductions, and not axiomatic ones as in Negri & vonPlato approach [15].

⁴Usually, in contemporary proof systems, elementary substitution is implicitly assumed via the use of metavariables.

§6. Conclusion. We has performed a journey to put consistency and provability together in a unique logical calculus. It began with a variant of a sequent calculus for classical propositional logic that integrates assumptions as postulates and as axioms, and in which deductions preserve consistency. This Hilbertian approach allowed us to prove the equivalence between provability and validity as well as between consistency and satisfiability, showing deep connections between cut, weakening and Post-completeness in sequent bicalculae. However, to really integrate SAT and SMT solvers with ATP systems we need to go, at least, to first-order logic. There are some works that already tried to formulate variants of the sequent calculus to analyze SMT, making constraints for first-order logic with linear integer arithmetic [4, 22]. Besides, sequent calculus may be useful to study computational complexity classes because we always have a complexity class and its dual in the same system - for instance, NP and $CoNP$ in the system explored here. There are works that explore the complexity of the DPLL algorithm formalized in terms of the resolution calculus as well as its relation to certain sequent calculus [12, 13]. Following these paths, we can build develop not only SAT solvers but also SMT solvers and ATP systems, all of them directly integrated in the same mathematical logic framework. Hilbert is known to have said: We must know, we will know. What has been proposed here is to re-state the Hilbert's motto: We must be direct, we will be direct!

REFERENCES

- [1] A. VORONKOV A. ROBINSON, *Handbook of automated reasoning*, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 2001.
- [2] W. ACKERMANN D. HILBERT, *Grundzüge der theoretischen logik*, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1928.
- [3] A. BALINT S. BAYLESS H. HOOS K. LEYTON-BROWN F. HUTTER, M. LINDAUER, *The configurable sat solver challenge (cssc)*, *Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 243 (2017), pp. 1–25.
- [4] R. CAUDERLIER D. DELAHAYE P. HALMAGRAND O. HERMANT G. BUREL, G. BURY, *First-order automated reasoning with theories: When proof modulo theory meets practice*, *Journal of Automated Reasoning*, vol. 64 (2020), pp. 1001–1050.
- [5] G. GENTZEN, *The collected papers of gerhard gentzen*, North-Holland Publisher, Amsterdam, 1969.
- [6] J.Y. GIRARD, *Proof theory and logical complexity*, Bibliopolis, Naples, 1987.
- [7] R.C. JEFFREY G.S. BOLOS, J.P. BURGESS, *Computability and logic*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2002.
- [8] A. GRIGGIO T. STURM C. TINELLI J. H. DAVENPORT, M. ENGLAND, *Symbolic computation and satisfiability checking*, *Journal of Symbolic Computation*, vol. 100 (2020), pp. 1–10.
- [9] M. KINYON, *Proof simplification and automated theorem proving*, *Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A*, vol. 377 (2018), no. 20180034, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2018.0034>.
- [10] G. KREISEL, *Friendliness and sympathy in logic*, *Logica universalis* (J.Y. Beziau, editor), Birkhauser Basel, Amsterdam, 2005, pp. 191–205.
- [11] N. BJORNER L. DE MOURA, *Satisfiability modulo theories: Introduction and applications*, *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 54 (2011), no. 9, pp. 69–77.
- [12] P. LIBERATORE, *Complexity results on dpll and resolution*, *ACM Transactions on Computational Logic*, vol. 7 (2006), no. 1, pp. 84–107.
- [13] A. MAHBOUBI M. FAROOQUE, S. GRAHAM-LENGRAND, *A bisimulation between dpll(t) and a proof-search strategy for the focused sequent calculus*, *ACM LFMT13*, vol. 23 (2013), pp. 1–13.

- [14] G. PULCINI M. PIAZZA, *Uniqueness of axiomatic extensions of cut-free classical propositional logic*, **Logic Journal of the IGPL**, vol. 24 (2016), no. 5, pp. 708–718.
- [15] S. NEGRI and J. VON PLATO, *Cut elimination in the presence of axioms*, **The Bulletin of Symbolic Logic**, vol. 4 (1998), no. 4, pp. 418–435.
- [16] ———, **Structural proof theory**, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2001.
- [17] ———, **Proof analysis**, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2011.
- [18] H. POINCARÉ, **La science et l'hypothèse**, Ernest Flammarion, Paris, 1917.
- [19] R. TAKEMURA, *Logic and majority voting*, **Journal of Philosophical Logic**, (2021), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10992-021-09631-7> 1-36.
- [20] A. TARSKI, **Logic, semantics, metamathematics**, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1983.
- [21] T. UESU, *A general method of axiomatizing fragments*, **Journal of Mathematical Society of Japan**, vol. 43 (1991), no. 2, pp. 23–35.
- [22] C. URBAN V. D'SILVA, *Abstract interpretation as automated deduction*, **Journal of Automated Reasoning**, vol. 58 (2017), pp. 363–390.
- [23] C. PIZZI W. CARNIELLI, **Modalities and multimodalities**, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 2008.

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